

Investigation of the Degree to which the Study of the Old Applied Mathematics Course Affected Students' Performance in Other Leaving Certificate Subjects

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In light of the recent reform of the Applied Mathematics course – offered in the Senior Cycle of Irish post-primary education but taken by comparatively few students – questions of interest are whether taking the old Applied Mathematics course affected performance in other subjects and whether the revised course will do likewise. With regard to the old course, the issue was addressed in a study that used a mixed-methods approach: a small-scale qualitative element examining teachers' and students' experiences of the course, and a larger-scale quantitative analysis. The focus in this paper is on the quantitative aspect and considers effects on Mathematics. The paper reports on the difference in students' performance in Mathematics from the Junior Certificate to the Leaving Certificate, comparing those who took Applied Mathematics with those who did not. The results show that taking Applied Mathematics had a strongly positive relationship with a change in performance in Mathematics. The study also demonstrates that the students in the Applied Mathematics group can be further divided into subpopulations based on change in performance in Mathematics.

Keywords: Curriculum reform; applied mathematics; attainment; high-stakes examinations

Introduction

The subject *Mathematics* has a prominent place in the Irish post-primary curriculum. In the Senior Cycle, it is not compulsory but is offered by almost all students who sit the Leaving Certificate examination, taken in the final year of schooling. For a long time, the main focus – especially of the most advanced course, Leaving Certificate Higher level – was on pure mathematics. This has changed to some extent recently, with more emphasis on applications to real-life situations; however, topics such as mechanics that appear in some Mathematics courses (for example in England) still do not figure greatly. They do appear in another Senior Cycle course, *Applied Mathematics* (henceforth Applied Maths). Uptake is small, and not all schools offer it, but it plays an important role for some students.

Applied mathematics can be described as the study of the practical applications of mathematics to the real world and physical problems. The Irish Applied Maths course was dominated by just the one field, mechanics; its topics – such as projectiles, pulley systems and collisions – were tested in discrete examination questions, leading to a very predictable examination structure. Several attempts were made to revise the subject, without success. Eventually the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) produced a discussion paper designed to lead to substantial reform (NCCA, 2014). Controversially, it asserted that the course encouraged a procedural approach rather than problem solving; this clashed with at least some perceptions that there was a strong problem-solving element,

perhaps even helping students to develop generalised skills that transferred to other subjects. A revised course has now been introduced (Department of Education, n.d.). While a strong mechanics component has been retained, new material – notably graph theory – has been introduced, and the course has been recast to focus explicitly on modelling. As with any curriculum change, questions arise as to gains and losses, and particularly in this case as to whether the criticisms of the old course were justified and the new one offers improvements.

The study on which this paper is based examined the old course, aiming to answer the following questions:

1. What were students' and teachers' experiences of Applied Maths?
2. Did studying Applied Maths develop problem-solving skills?
3. To what degree did the skills developed through studying Applied Maths transfer to different domains?

The work was the first author's final-year undergraduate project, which was supervised by the second author. A mixed-methods approach was used. The small-scale qualitative element chiefly addressed the first research question; the larger-scale quantitative analysis examined data from the State examinations – Junior Certificate and Leaving Certificate – and compared aspects of the performance in selected subjects of students who did and who did not take Applied Maths, with a view to answering the third question. This paper focuses on the quantitative component. However, in interpreting the quantitative findings, it draws heavily on the results of the qualitative component, which are presented in the literature review.

Literature Review

To address the research questions, three areas of research are relevant: problem solving, transfer of skills, and consideration of the old Applied Mathematics course. They are addressed in turn.

In order to consider *problem solving*, it is necessary first to clarify what is meant by a problem. Mathematics educators agree that a problem is a situation which ... carries with it certain open questions that challenge somebody intellectually who is not in immediate possession of direct methods/procedures/algorithms etc. sufficient to answer the questions. (Blum & Niss, 1991, p. 37)

A consequence of this is that whether a question is a problem or only an exercise is dependent not only on the person tackling the question, but also at what point in time that person is doing so. What may be a routine exercise for a person today may have been a problem for them yesterday. In the extensive literature on problem solving, the work of Schoenfeld (1992) on the characteristics of *good problems* and Menary (2015) on *enculturation* is notable. According to this, a crucial aspect of mathematical development is acquiring the habits, beliefs, and attitudes of mathematicians as well as expanding one's knowledge base. If so, the development of problem-solving ability may be best encouraged by allowing students to experience problems in the way that an "expert" does. This suggests that students should be afforded the opportunity to act as mathematicians within the classroom.

Transfer consists of “[applying] previously learned knowledge with various degrees of adaptation or modification of that knowledge in completing a task or solving problems” (Hung, 2013, p. 27). This has frequently been described as a highly important goal of education, though according to Haskell (2000) it is very difficult to achieve in any significant way. Johnson (1995) differentiates between *near* and *far* transfer. However, it might be more accurate to think about transfer on a continuum; Thorndike’s theory of transfer asserts that the amount of transfer from one situation to another is proportional to the degree of similarity between the two situations (Woodworth & Thorndike, 1901).

With regard to *the old Applied Maths* course, there is a paucity of research. The discussion paper produced by the NCCA (2014) as a background to reviewing the course provides some context on its history and low uptake, noting that fewer than 3% of students in the Leaving Certificate cohort presented the subject. As indicated above, the paper asserts that it is procedure-focused, reportedly being studied through intensive practice of past examination papers in particular; comments from third-level students are included in support of this view. A response by the Irish Mathematics Teachers’ Association (2014) provides additional context on the history of Applied Maths, mentioning past unsuccessful attempts at reform. In contradiction to the NCCA view, and drawing on feedback from members who taught Applied Maths, it asserts that the subject promotes problem solving.

The study by Curran (2023) addresses the conflicting claims. Small convenience samples of teacher volunteers (four, all experienced teachers of Applied Maths) and third-level students (seven, all of whom had taken the subject) were interviewed about their general experience of the subject and were asked about the pedagogical and learning approaches they believed were encouraged by the curriculum and examinations. While the findings from such small convenience samples may not generalise, they offer potential insights. The teachers and students agreed that the examination papers were predictable, consisting of about 75% routine/familiar material and about 25% that was challenging/novel. However, the teachers emphasised understanding and problem solving as the keys to success, whereas the students focused more on practice and repetition. Curran (2023) points out that apparent discrepancies may be somewhat reconciled as suggested by the words of one teacher interviewee:

You mustn’t forget that in the month we did studying it, we started not knowing how to learn to do those questions. Especially if it’s well taught, in other words, in, you know, not just, here’s a nifty little way, but you have to understand what’s going on and you understand why. (T2) (Curran, 2023, p. 56)

In other words, the problem-solving element may figure in (appropriate) initial teaching and learning, rather than when students are approaching and taking the examination. A possibly relevant finding here was that there was more reported diversity in the teachers’ pedagogical approaches than in the students’ learning strategies. With regard to transfer, the teachers and students agreed that Applied Maths helped Mathematics and Physics, but the students had a more conservative view of the benefits for other subjects, whereas the teachers had a greater appreciation for the role of Applied Maths in developing general problem-solving skills.

Methodology

This section describes the methodology for the main, quantitative element of Curran's (2023) project. Analysis of data from the third and fourth wave of the *Growing up in Ireland* study was undertaken. This study follows the progress of approximately 8,000 children, beginning in 2006 when they were eight years of age, and includes data on their Junior Certificate and Leaving Certificate results for English, Irish, and Mathematics – the three subjects taken (in both examinations) by the vast majority of students. Also included is whether students took Applied Maths in the Leaving Certificate. Research question 3 above was modified for this data set as follows:

- 3a. Did students who took the old Applied Maths course improve from the Junior Certificate to the Leaving Certificate in Mathematics, English and/or Irish, in relation to their peers?

Access to the relevant examination results was obtained from the Irish Social Science Data Archive, with help from Prof. Emer Smyth of the Economic and Social Research. The dataset in question is very detailed and had to be narrowed down significantly. While some information such as socioeconomic factors could be relevant in a larger study investigating who has access to and opts to take Applied Maths, the author did not have permission to use data other than students' results. Anyway, the issues that could have been addressed in such a study were outside the scope and timescale of this already substantial undergraduate project.

Data was cleaned by excluding participants with missing or incomprehensible data (for example, Leaving Certificate points for Mathematics greater than the maximum possible score of 125: *points* being the metric used to map Leaving Certificate examination grades onto a numerical scale to rank-order students applying for places on third-level courses). For each subject, Leaving Certificate results were ranked by the points; Junior Certificate results were ranked first by level – Higher / Ordinary / Foundation – and then by grade. The rankings were then transformed into percentile scores. Correlations between the scores were investigated; for example, correlations between students' Mathematics scores at Junior Certificate and at Leaving Certificate were computed.

For each student, the difference between the two percentile scores for a subject was calculated so as to measure improvement/regression of students *relative to their peers*. (It should be noted that students taking Applied Maths are usually high performers overall. The focus here is therefore on gains/losses over the period in which they studied Applied Maths, rather than just on Leaving Certificate scores.) A logistic regression was performed to investigate the relationship between this difference and whether or not a student took Applied Maths; the regression coefficient was tested for significance. Also, clustering techniques were used to investigate the possible existence of subpopulations within the data. The approach was authenticated by consultation with statistician Jason Wyse in Trinity College; technical details are outside the scope of this paper.

Results

Results presented here are limited to the findings for Mathematics. First, it should be noted that results in Mathematics at the two levels are highly correlated ($r = 0.80$). This suggests that skills tested in the Mathematics Junior Certificate and Mathematics Leaving Certificate examinations have very significant overlap.

Table 1

Average Mathematics Results (Applied Maths Students)

Applied Maths Students	Average Percentile
Junior Certificate Mathematics	81.76
Leaving Certificate Mathematics	88.52

The percentile rankings confirm that, on average, Applied Maths students performed above their peers in both Junior Certificate and Leaving Certificate (Table 1). Thus, the issue of interest is whether the Applied Maths students performed above their peers *to a greater extent* in the Leaving Certificate. Table 1 shows that there was a substantial improvement in percentile ranking from Junior Certificate to Leaving Certificate for those who studied Applied Maths, with a mean increase of 6.76 percentile points. A logistic regression determined this relationship to be highly significant with a p-value of 1.28×10^{-11} . However, while students who took Applied Maths improved in Mathematics by a considerable amount on average, relative to their peers, it is not immediately evident if this can be attributed directly to the skills developed by Applied Maths.

Figure 1

Distribution of Change in Mathematics Results: Applied Maths and Non-Applied Maths students

The distribution of the results paints a more complete picture. As can be seen from Figure 1, the distribution of changes in performance in Mathematics among Applied Maths students is entirely different from that of the rest of the population. The “bumps” in the distribution of Applied Maths students’ scores suggests the existence of subpopulations:

- a small minority for whom Applied Maths has a significant negative impact (a decrease of 10-30 percentile points)
- the majority for whom Applied Maths has a positive impact (an increase of 0-10 percentile points)
- a significant minority for whom Applied Maths has an extremely positive impact (an increase of 20-45 percentile points).

Clustering techniques confirmed the existence of the subpopulations within the data; details of this analysis are outside the scope of the paper.

Overall, therefore, it can be said that the students who take Applied Maths do, as a whole, improve in those skills tested in Mathematics, relative to their peers (research question 3a). To what degree this might be attributed to Applied Maths itself is discussed below.

Discussion

The results from the quantitative study give a positive answer to the modified research question 3a for Mathematics. Since Mathematics and Applied Mathematics are cognate subjects, perhaps this is not surprising in light of Thorndike’s theory of transfer noted above (the amount of transfer from one situation to another being proportional to the degree of similarity between the two situations (Woodworth & Thorndike, 1901)). However, the original research question 3 is not fully addressed, as the findings do not indicate the nature of the skills that may have transferred to the study of Mathematics, except insofar as they are examined in the Junior and Leaving Certificate Mathematics examinations. This is now discussed in relation to the other literature reviewed, particularly with regard to the debate as to whether the old Applied Maths course promoted problem-solving in the sense that the term is used in mathematics education literature, distinguishing problems from routine exercises.

Confirmation by clustering techniques of subpopulations in the data only for the Applied Maths students indicates there are subgroups of students who are experiencing Applied Maths in some way differently. The question arises as to what these different experiences might be. The comment from a teacher in Curran’s (2023) qualitative study, quoted above, may provide a clue; the teacher indicated that topics could be *introduced* in a way that developed understanding and problem solving, whereas later the focus would be on preparing for (predictable) examinations through intensive practice. If the old Applied Maths course were taught in the manner that this teacher describes, that is as a guided investigation, the first year’s work would consist of students being introduced to most of the topics that they would cover. In that first year, students would experience mathematics in the way that mathematicians do: as an exploratory and investigative process, which can develop confidence in one’s competency as a problem solver and the perseverance associated with that. Exploring the deep questions at the heart of topics offers all the characteristics of a good

problem outlined by Schoenfeld (2016). If topics were treated in this way, the old Applied Maths course may well have had the potential to improve problem-solving skills. It is conjectured here that such an experience of the old Applied Maths course characterises the subpopulation of Applied Maths students who improved dramatically in Mathematics.

Unfortunately, it seems that most students did not have the experience of Applied Maths outlined above. In such instances, teachers may have put more emphasis on procedural fluency throughout the course than on constructing understanding and problem solving. One might expect students who had this experience of Applied Maths to improve somewhat in Mathematics purely due to the additional practice. It is conjectured that this characterises the subpopulation of Applied Maths students who improved in Mathematics, but by less than 10 percentile points. (No conjecture is offered here with regard to those who regressed.)

Overall, the evidence suggests that the old Applied Maths course had the potential, though often left unrealised, to facilitate significant near transfer (in Johnson's (1995) terminology) of problem-solving skills, if appropriately taught. The richness of the topics and the narrow scope of the course could promote this, as they allowed the opportunity for students to delve deeply into a small number of rich investigations.

Conclusion

The main aim of the study on which this paper is based was to investigate the effect that studying the old Applied Maths course had on other subjects. This paper reports findings with regard to Mathematics. The strength of the old Applied Maths course appears to have been in its potential – not always realised – for extremely significant near transfer to Mathematics, via the development of students' problem-solving skills and confidence in their capabilities as mathematicians. If the style of teaching that encouraged this could be more broadly implemented, it would represent a very powerful tool in mathematics education.

It is important to be aware of the limitations of this study. There are many factors that cannot be controlled for, so the overlap between studying Applied Maths and improved performance in Mathematics may not be causal. In particular, the mechanisms behind the presence of subpopulations among Applied Maths students, while informed by qualitative and quantitative research and the present literature on the subject, are merely conjectures, and are not backed by concrete evidence.

Additional research is required to investigate the effect that studying Applied Maths had on subjects other than Mathematics. (The work has already been done for English and Irish; however, the findings are outside the scope of this paper.) The first author hopes to be granted access to the more detailed files of the study, which will allow investigation of all the subjects that appear in both the Junior Cycle and the Leaving Certificate. Furthermore, the study provides a template for analysing the effect subject "x" has on performance in subject "y". There is little reason going forward to restrict "x" to be Applied Maths.

Further research within the next decade will be required to analyse whether the strengths of the old course have been kept in the new Applied Maths course, and whether the

weaknesses of the old course have been improved upon. Initial research could perhaps utilise data from the infant cohort of the *Growing up in Ireland* study, the majority of whom will be sitting their Leaving Certificate examinations in 2024. The findings could then help to shape implementation and perhaps adjustment of the new course, and further data might be collected to monitor its role in the years to come.

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